

Early Warning Systems for *Gambierdiscus* and other benthic harmful algae: sampling challenges

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Abstract

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) is a long-neglected foodborne disease affecting tropical regions of the Pacific and Indian Oceans and the Caribbean Sea. CP was raised by the Pacific Nations at the 32nd Session of the FAO Committee on Fisheries in 2016. In 2017, it was an agenda item at the 11th Session of the Codex Committee on Contaminants in Foods. The committee requested scientific advice from FAO and WHO, so late 2018 a group of experts met to develop the Joint FAO-WHO Report of the Expert Meeting on Ciguatera Poisoning that provided risk management options for CP. In parallel with this, an interagency global ciguatera strategy was developed among FAO, IOC, IAEA and WHO. Building on these initiatives, these three UN Agencies convened an expert meeting to develop Joint FAO, IOC, IAEA Technical guidance for the implementation of Early Warning Systems (EWSs) for harmful algal blooms (HABs). The EWS approach includes monitoring protocols for sampling benthic genera like *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* that produce toxins responsible for CP. Advances in *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* taxonomy, better understanding of their global distribution and toxicity and species-specific molecular identification and enumeration methods help make this possible.

Keywords: Artificial substrate, cell-based early warning system, *Ostreopsis*, *Prorocentrum*

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Introduction

Key to standardizing a protocol for cell based EWS for *Gambierdiscus* is how, when, and where to sample. Unlike planktonic species, there is no agreed upon, sampling method for harmful, benthic microalgal species (BHABs). We fully appreciate that pelagic phytoplankton sampling techniques have been refined over a century and it is completely accepted that planktonic phytoplankton cells are normalized to the volume of water collected.

Traditionally, benthic epiphytic cells abundances are normalized to grams wet weight of the macrophytes that serve as substrates. There are myriad arguments against this collection technique, including ignoring the use of more accurate, surface-area normalized cell densities and habitat destruction. Artificial substrates, rather than macrophytes, are proposed as sampling platforms so cell abundances can be normalized to surface areas rather than biomass. We hope to open a dialog among interested colleagues and invite them to develop proof of concept projects comparing traditional macrophyte sampling methods with artificial substrates.

Historically, the mismatch between normalizing BHAB cell abundance to wet weight (biomass) or to host surface area was recognized. Lobel *et al.* (1988) observed a nearly four-fold difference in the ratio of wet weight to surface area between the two macrophytes, *Dictyota* and *Galaxaura*, despite having equivalent mass to volume ratios (1.05 and 0.96, respectively). Estimates of *Gambierdiscus* cell densities from these macroalgae varied greatly depending on

whether they were normalized to mass or surface area (Lobel *et al.*, agreed with Bomber *et al.* (1985);

“Analysis of these data demonstrate the misleading nature of dinoflagellate abundance expressed per gram of host alga and provides a good argument for yet another change to common enumeration methodologies – namely the normalization of dinoflagellate abundance to host surface area rather than biomass “

While normalization of cell abundance to macrophyte surface area was the correct way to sample, very few researchers have taken the time to make the tedious measurements of macrophyte surface area. Such measurements are incredibly time consuming and not feasible for use in monitoring programs.

Another complication, an unstated assumption, associated with macrophyte based sampling is that *Gambierdiscus* and other BHABs, prefer to settle on specific macrophyte species. The available field data, however, do not support this (Fig. 1). Data from 60 published studies show no consistency in the same macrophyte groups harboring the highest *Gambierdiscus* cell densities, these macrophytes, as well as other substrates such as turf algae, do have in common a greater surface area per gram of tissue compared to the other macrophytes sampled in the various studies. In many habitats, high density species are the foliose macrophytes, but these species are not always present (Lee *et al.*, 2020).

The reason the cell concentration in seawater to cell density per surface area relationship

exists is the frequent movement of BHAB cells into the water column and their settlement on new surfaces. The larger the population of BHAB species, the greater the proportion of cells that detach from their substrate. Where these cells will land is highly stochastic, but on average, the predominant macrophytes with the highest surface area per gram will recruit the greater number of cells, simply by chance. In this case, when abundances are expressed as cells g^{-1} wet weight algae, the higher surface area species will, on average, harbor more cells. The higher density is not due to active “preference” but due to stochastically landing on substrates having the highest surface area per unit biomass.

Fig. 1. Classes of macrophytes, turf algae and coral reported to support the highest *Gambierdiscus* densities. Data are from 60 journal articles published between 1970 and 2021.

A further complication of sampling macrophytes is that high abundances of *Gambierdiscus* and other BHAB species can occur in habitats lacking macrophytes. Lee

et al. (2018) sampled different habitat types and found that *Gambierdiscus* was most abundant on turf algae, a carpet of different species covering the surface of rocks or other hard substrates. The second highest cell abundances were found on hard coral and the third most abundant counts were from habitats with fleshy or foliose algae. Clearly, a less habitat dependent method is required for collecting BHABs for quantification of toxic cell for early warning systems.

To develop a sound monitoring program, a standardized, universal, and unbiased sampling protocol is needed. The method also should allow comparisons of data across different habitats, locations, time periods (seasons) and bloom phases. To address this need, we propose an artificial substrate sampling method, where cells are recruited from the surrounding substrates and cell abundance can be normalized to surface, not to biomass. This approach allows samples to be taken in the different habitats using a statistically robust sampling method which is key to any effective monitoring program.

Methods and Results

Many artificial substrates could be used but we selected window screen mesh. It is readily available, inert, light weight and inexpensive enough to be disposable so there is no possibility for cells to be carried over to cause contamination. A carefully measured piece of window screen is suspended between a weight and a float on a shortline, so the entire sampling device is sub surface to avoid any disturbance from waves and swells (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Artificial substrate sampling device with window screen mesh suspended between a weight and a subsurface float to keep the screen suspended approximately 5 cm off the bottom

It is important to calculate the surface area of the mesh fibers, not just the overall dimensions of the piece of screen (Tester *et al.*, 2014). For sampling high concentrations of *Ostreopsis* a frame has been added to help support the screen and in high energy areas it is useful to keep the mesh screen from folding back on itself (Jauzein *et al.*, 2018; Fernández-Zabala *et al.*, 2019). Screens are retrieved after 24 h, and the cells dislodged for counting. Cell abundances are reported in cells cm⁻².

For *Gambierdiscus* 24 h is the optimal sampling or loading time for the mesh screens. From 6 h through 24 h cells recruit to the screens. This observation is consistent with the BHAB species moving around and colonizing free space in proportion to the overall abundance of cells in the surrounding environment. The concentration of cells

on the screens does not increase after 24 h (Tester *et al.*, 2014; Fernández-Zabala *et al.*, 2019). This loading pattern suggests a diel rhythm for the cells to release from substrates, swim and be transported in the water column and then resettle (Fernández-Zabala *et al.*, 2019; Fig. 3) This same pattern was observed for *Ostreopsis* loading on three replicate screens over a 24-h period (Jauzein *et al.*, 2018). Given the success of a frame to support sampling screens, we recommend its use.

When cells g⁻¹ wet weight of macrophyte host are plotted against cells cm⁻², there is a reasonable correspondence in the data from *Gambierdiscus* (Fig. 3) and *Ostreopsis* (Jauzein *et al.*, 2018). In each of the *Gambierdiscus* studies below five or more replicates were used (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. *Gambierdiscus* abundance comparison using macrophyte hosts (cells g⁻¹ wet weight) and artificial substrate (cells cm⁻²). Data from Tester *et al.* (2014) and Fernández-Zabala *et al.* (2019).

These data suggest screens samplers are as capable of estimating cell densities in habitats dominated by macrophytes as directly

sampling the macrophytes themselves. This is further support for using screen sampling for monitoring programs. It should be noted this is a log-log plot and though the relationship of cell densities estimated using both methods are relatively good, the highly patchy distribution of BHAB cells means that, regardless of the sampling method, variability around mean cell estimates will be high. This leads us to a discussion of the importance of replicate samples.

With patchy distributions of BHAB cells, how many replicate samples are required to achieve cell estimates with standard errors of the mean less than 100%? The lower the cell abundance, the more replicates are needed to achieve the lowest possible coefficient of variation (CV, %). A power analysis is needed to determine the adequate number of replicates (Lobel *et al.*, 1988; Tester *et al.*, 2014). For example, with low numbers of cells a minimum of 10 replicates or more are needed. If cell abundance is high, (more than 100 cells cm⁻²) five replicates would be expected to produce a CV of 50% of the mean (Tester *et al.*, 2014). To reduce the CV, it is imperative to sample adequate numbers of replicates, or the data will not be meaningful. In contrast, for very high numbers (e.g. > 50,000 *Ostreopsis* or *Prorocentrum* cells cm⁻²) three replicates could be sufficient.

The need to wait for 24 h to ensure a representative collection of cells in the screens, constitutes a drawback of this method. However, samples are cleaner for cell counting, toxin determination and molecular identification.

Advantages and Recommendations

Artificial substrates allow cell counts to be normalized to surface area and supports randomized sampling regimes that are less biased than depending on specific macrophytes whose density and location can change over time. The screen samples, in the water for 24 h, integrate cells originating from multiple sources so they provide a better estimate of cell densities in structurally complex habitats where it is not possible to sample different substrate types equally well.

It is necessary for any monitoring program to determine the BHAB species present as well. Species composition matters because *Gambierdiscus* species-specific toxicities can vary by more than 1,000-fold with intraspecific toxicities varying 100-fold and seasonal toxicity changes are possible as well (Chinain *et al.*, 2010; Litaker *et al.*, 2017; Rossignoli *et al.*, 2020). Studies from each part of the globe inform us about the difference in species toxicity. By making a preliminary survey on the major toxin producing species in the monitoring area (Smith *et al.*, 2017), molecular techniques can be used to quickly identify increased abundance of target species.

Because toxic and nontoxic BHAB species are often quite difficult to identify using light microscopy, species-specific qPCR represents an alternative for quantifying cell densities. These assays are easier to perform using screen samples because they are less susceptible to interference from debris which is a major problem when using cells from macrophytes. The qPCR assays are also easy to scale up for large numbers of samples. The combination of clean samples collected

from screens followed by species- specific qPCR is the backbone of a Cell Based Early Warning System for Benthic HABs.

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